

Spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II) in environmental, soil, medicinal and biological samples using 2-benzoylpyridine-4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (BPMT)

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Abstract : Analytical and biological applications of 2-benzoylpyridine-4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (BPMT) are reported for the first time. The reagent (BPMT) has been synthesized and characterized by IR, NMR, and mass spectral data. BPMT reacts with mercury(II) in slightly acidic medium (pH 6.0 sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer) to form deep yellow coloured complex. The complex shows maximum absorbance at 410 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the method are found to be $4.7 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0103 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of mercury(II). The composition of the complex is found to be 1 : 1 (M : L). The method is successfully applied to a number of environmental, biological, medicinal and soil samples. The results are comparable with those obtained by dithizone method. The proposed system has high sensitivity, accuracy and precision ($s = 0.078$ for $4 \mu\text{g/ml}$ in BPMT method).

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, mercury determination, 2-benzoylpyridine-4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazone, water, medicinal, biological and soil samples.

Introduction

The analytical monitoring of mercury in environmental, biological, industrial and food samples is extremely important because of the high toxicity of this metal both in its inorganic and organic compounds¹. An example for acute mercury poisoning is "Mina-mata disease" which causes mental disturbance, a loss of balance, speech, sight and hearing, difficulty in swallowing and finally coma and death². The toxicity of mercury depends on its chemical nature. Inorganic mercury(II) reacts with proteins' sulfhydryl groups (Scheme 1), and makes enzyme inactive. It also accumulates in kidneys. Organic mercury is more toxic³ since it is soluble in fat, the lipid fractions of membranes, and brain tissue. Mercury toxicity is caused mainly by the fact that it enters the living organism and reacts with different enzymes inhibiting the catalysis of basic metabolic reactions⁴.

Scheme 1. The reaction of Hg^{II} with an enzyme.

In the light of the above, determination of mercury in biological sample using simple methods is an attractive and interesting activity of analytical chemist. Thiosemicarbazones are interesting chromogenic reagents⁵⁻⁷. Thiosemicarbazones having pyridine group have attracted considerable attention^{8,9}. This class of reagents gives intense coloured complexes, show more bathochromic shift, more sensitivity and selectivity. The selectivity of thiosemicarbazone, however, may be improved by incorporating hydrophobic groups like methyl, phenyl, nitro etc. With this idea in mind we have synthesized 2-benzoylpyridine-4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (BPMT) and explored its analytical properties. The potential biological applications of this class of compounds are explored quite recently. Substituted derivatives of 2'-benzoylpyridine thiosemicarbazone chelators exhibit selective antiproliferative activity¹⁰, neoplastic activity and known to limit methemoglobin formation¹¹. The structurally related di-2-pyridylketone thiosemicarbazone shows potent activity against lung cancer¹². This paper describes the non-extractive spectrophotometric determination of

mercury(II) as its BPMT complex in aqueous medium. A close literature survey reveals that BPMT is not so far employed for the spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II).

Results and discussion

The reagent, 2-benzoylpyridine-4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (BPMT) is easily prepared. The compound is characterized by IR, NMR and mass spectral data. Infrared spectrum of BPMT shows bands (cm^{-1}) at 3296(s), 3056(m), 2936(m), 1585(s), and 1045(s) respectively assigned to $\nu(\text{NH})$ secondary, (C-H) aromatic stretch (sp^2 C-H), $\nu(\text{C-H})$ aliphatic stretching, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ Schiff base and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibrations respectively. ^1H NMR spectrum of BPMT ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$) shows signals (δ ppm) at 3.23 (3H, s), 8.90 (1H, s), 13.72 (1H, s) and 7.3–7.8 (9H, m) due to $-\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{NH}$, $>\text{NH}-$ (imino) and aromatic and pyridine protons of BPMT respectively. Mass spectrum shows molecular ion peak at m/z 271. Other peaks due to loss of methyl ($\cdot\text{CH}_3$) and $\text{NH}-\text{CH}_3$ radicals are also observed in the mass spectrum. Based on the above spectral data, the structure of the reagent is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Structure of 2-benzoylpyridine-4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (BPMT).

Absorption spectra of $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ solution of BPMT at different pH values are recorded and pK_a values are determined spectrophotometrically using Phillip and Merritt method¹³. The bathochromic shift from 280 to 350 nm indicates that in solution on increasing pH the $>\text{C}=\text{S}$ group of reagent (BPMT) is enolised and dissociated (Scheme 2). The values of deprotonation constants of BPMT are found to be 3.3 (pK_1) and 9.0 (pK_2) respectively. The pK_1 and pK_2 values are presumably due to thione-thiol tautomerism and deprotonation of thiol (SH) group respectively.

A 0.01 M solution of reagent is stable for 12 h. The colour reactions of metal ions with the reagent are summarized in Table 1. At higher pHs (>4) the ligand presumably exists in enolic form. The colour reaction of reagent with mercury(II) is found to be instantaneous even at room temperature. The order of addition of reagent, metal ion, and buffer has no effect on the absorbance of the complex. Various physico-chemical and analytical characteristics of Hg-BPMT complex are summarized in Table 2. Stoichiometry of the complex [1 : 1 (M : L)] is determined by Job's continuous variation method¹⁴ and molar ratio method. Sodium acetate (0.2 M)-acetic acid solution (0.2 M) buffer (pH 6.0, $\mu = 0.2$ and $T = 300 \text{ K}$) and equimolar solution of mercury(II) and reagent are used in these studies. The dissociation constant (α) and concentration (c) of the reagent at intersecting point are used in the calculation of stability constant (eq. (1)) of the complex.

$$\beta = \frac{1 - \alpha}{\alpha^2 c} \quad (1)$$

Scheme 2. Chemical equilibrium between a keto and enol forms of BPMT.

Table 1. Chromogenic characteristics of BPMT

Metal ion	λ_{\max} (nm)	Molar absorptivity, ϵ ($L \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	pH range	Colour of the complex
Cu ^{II}	410	1.45×10^4	5.0–8.0	Yellow
Hg ^{II}	410	4.70×10^4	5.0–8.0	Greenish yellow
Co ^{II}	380	1.04×10^4	5.0–8.0	Orange yellow
Ni ^{II}	390	2.00×10^4	6.0–8.0	Yellow
Zn ^{II}	390	3.02×10^4	5.0–8.0	Pale yellow
Cd ^{II}	400	1.60×10^4	7.0–10.0	Greenish yellow
Pb ^{II}	390	2.9×10^4	5.0–7.0	Pale yellow

Table 2. Physico-chemical and analytical characteristics of Hg^{II}-BPMT complex

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Results
1.	λ_{\max} (nm)	410
2.	Mean absorbance	0.248 ± 0.0006
3.	pH range (optimum)	5–8
4.	Mole of reagent required for mole of metal ion for full colour development	10-fold
5.	Time stability of the complex (h)	12
6.	Beer's law validity range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.80–7.20
7.	Molar absorptivity ($L \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	4.7×10^4
8.	Specific absorptivity ($\text{ml g}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	0.0997
9.	Sandell's sensitivity (μg) of Hg ^{II} (cm^{-2})	0.0103
10.	Composition of the complex as obtained in Job's and molar ratio methods	1 : 1
11.	Stability constant of the complex	2.06×10^5
12.	Standard deviation(s) in the determination of $4.0 \mu\text{g/ml}$ of Hg ^{II} for ten determinations	0.078
13.	Relative standard deviation (RSD), or coefficient of variation	3.088%

Tolerance limits of foreign ions : The effect of various diverse ions which often accompany mercury has been studied by adding different amounts of foreign ions and fixed amount of mercury(II) in solution. The colour reaction is studied in the presence of foreign ions as described in the recommended procedure. An error of ± 2 percent in the absorbance of the reaction mixture is considered tolerable. The results are given in Table 3. Cadmium(II) and cobalt(II) seriously interfere in the present method. The interferences of these metal ions are masked with $200 \mu\text{g/mL}$ of thiocyanate.

Table 3. Tolerance limits of foreign ions in the determination of $3.209 \mu\text{g/ml}$ of Hg^{II}

Ion added	Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Ion added	Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Citrate	384	W ^{VI}	185
Tartrate	296	Mn ^{II}	110
Iodate	254	Mg ^{II}	4.9
Bicarbonate	244	Pb ^{II}	4.2
Thiocyanate	232	Cd ^{II}	11 ^a
Sulphate	192	Pb ^{II}	10
Oxalate	176	Cr ^{VI}	7
Nitrate	124	Fe ^{II}	6
Acetate	118	Zn ^{II}	5
Phosphate	20	Cu ^{II}	3
Bromide	16	Co ^{II}	1.3 ^a
Chloride	7.1	Ni ^{II}	0.47
Flouride	4.0	Au ^{III}	0.40
		Pt ^{IV}	0.39
		Ag ^I	0.22
		V ^V	0.20

^aMasked with $200 \mu\text{g/ml}$ of thiocyanate.

Applications : The present method is successfully applied to the determination of Hg^{II} when present alone. The developed method is also applied to the determination of Hg^{II} in water samples, soil, medicinal and biological samples. The results (Table 4) obtained in the analysis of different samples are comparable to the data obtained using dithizone method¹⁵.

Table 4. Determination of mercury in water, soil, medicinal and biological samples

Name of the samples	Amount of mercury ^a found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	
	BPMT method	Dithizone method
Drain water ^e	3.931	3.762
Laboratory water ^d	3.43	3.29
Sea water ^c	1.142	1.003
Tap water ^f	0.764	0.695
Well water ^g	0.863	0.842
River water ^b	0.621	0.614
Urban soil	1.59	1.55
Agricultural soil	0.448	0.412
Road side soil	1.588	1.553
Brain damage patient	0.897	0.865
Kidney damage patient	0.912	0.879
Paralysis patient	1.485	1.472
Fish liver	2.91	2.89
Sheep liver	0.983	0.918

Table-4 (contd.)

Ayurvedic medicinal samples		
Siddamakaradhvaj	0.495	0.497
Panchabhanaras	1.605	1.603
Vasanthakusumakaram	0.965	0.981

^aAverage of three determinations. ^bTungabhadra river water (Kurnool), ^cBay of Bengal (Chennai), ^dLaboratory water (Department of Chemistry, S. K. University, Anantapur), ^eAnantapur town, drain water, ^fAnantapur municipal storage tank water.

Conclusions

The present method is simple, rapid and sensitive without the need for heating or extraction. Further, the reagent is easy to synthesize using commercially available 2-benzoylpyridine. The present work describes a facile spectrophotometric method which is applied to various water, biological and medicinal samples.

Experimental

Preparation of BPMT : The reagent was prepared by simple condensation of 2-benzoylpyridine (0.0155 mol, 2.5 ml) dissolved in 10 ml of methanol and 4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (0.0155 mol, 1.63 g) dissolved in 10 ml of hot distilled water. Suitable quantity (~2 ml) of glacial acetic acid was added and heated under reflux with stirring for 5 h. Shiny deep yellow crystals were separated out on cooling the reaction mixture. It was collected by filtration and washed with hot water and with 1 : 1 cold methanol. The compound was recrystallized from methanol and dried in vacuum. Yield 92%, m.p. 145–147 °C.

The reagent solution (0.01 M) was prepared by dissolving 67 mg of the compound in 25 ml of dimethylformamide (DMF) and it is stable for more than 12 h.

Hydrochloric acid (1 M)-sodium acetate(1 M) (pH 0.5–3.5); 0.2 M sodium acetate-0.2 M acetic acid (pH 4.0–6.5) and 0.2 M ammonium chloride-0.2 M ammonium solutions (pH 7.5–10.5) was used in the present study.

The standard (1×10^{-2} M) stock solution of divalent mercury was prepared by using analytical reagent grade 0.272 g of HgCl₂ (Merck, Darmstadt) in deionized water containing few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid and made up to the mark in a 100-ml volumetric flask. Aliquots of this solution were standardised¹⁶ with EDTA using xylenol orange as an indicator. Dilute solutions were prepared from this stock solution. Solutions of all

inorganic ions, complexing agents were prepared from their AnalaR grade water soluble salts.

Recommended procedure :

A known aliquot of the Hg^{II} solution was taken in a 25-ml standard flask containing 10 ml of buffer solution of pH 6.0 and 1.5 ml 1×10^{-2} M reagent solution. The contents are made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 410 nm against the reagent (BPMT) blank. The absorbance values were referred to the predetermined calibration plot and computed the amount of mercury in sample solutions. Shimadzu 160A UV-Visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm (path length) quartz cells and Elico Model LI-120 pH meter were used in present study.

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